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30 March 1971
~~31st~~ December 1970

H.E. Mehrdad Pahlbod,
Minister of Culture,
Ministry of Culture,
Teheran.

Your Excellency,

I wish to make a formal application to renew my permit for archaeological surface survey of Islamic sites in southern Iran and on the coast and islands of the Persian Gulf which I carried out in 1968 and 1969-1970 with the esteemed permission and assistance of the Iranian Archaeological Service. I wish to complete my survey between June and September 1971 and propose to limit my work strictly to the surface investigation of sites. I do not intend to conduct any excavation during this period.

I intend to make a record of all sites visited by noting their size, location, morphology, and type of settlement, by collecting a representative selection of the surface pottery and porcelain, and by the recording of standing monuments, especially those such as caravansarais directly related to the major trading role of the area. I will produce maps of the distribution of different types of Islamic pottery in this area, of the size and location of settlements at different periods, and of the major trade routes running inland from the Persian Gulf in the Islamic Period.

At the end of this survey I will submit a complete gazetteer and list of sites to the Iranian Archaeological Service, and will thereafter prepare my research for publication.

My research is sponsored by The British Institute of Persian Studies and by Oxford University. Miss Martha Prickett of Harvard University, Fellow of the National Science Foundation of Washington, D.C., will assist.

The area which I intend to investigate archaeologically is:

- 1) In the Province of the Ports and Islands of the Persian Gulf and Sea of Oman: The Persian Gulf coast from Bandar Deylam to Minab, and the islands of Qeshm and Hormuz.
- 2) In Kerman Province: The Islamic routes inland from Bandar Abbas to Jiruft and to Sirjan.
- 3) In Fars Province: The valleys inland from the coast between Bandar Siraf and Lar.

I am your obedient servant,

A.G. Williamson

A.G. Williamson.
Fellow, The British Institute of
Persian Studies.